

Learning-based nonlinear predictive controller for solar thermal collector fields

Igor M. L. Pataro, Juan D. Gil, José D. Álvarez, José L. Guzmán *Member, IEEE*, João M. Lemos *Senior Member, IEEE*, Manuel Berenguel, *Senior Member, IEEE*

Abstract—Effectively controlling solar collector fields (SCFs) is crucial for optimizing solar thermal energy production. However, the nonlinear SCF dynamics, model parameter uncertainty, and the constantly disturbed nature of the system pose significant challenges for control strategies. This study introduces a novel Learning Practical Nonlinear Model Predictive Controller (LPNMPC) to address offset-free error related to model mismatch and unmodeled disturbances within the control framework. Motivated by the limitations of existing practical nonlinear predictive strategies, the LPNMPC leverages an adaptive Oracle function computed using Recursive Least Squares (RLS) with Exponential Resetting (ER) to estimate model errors. This approach improves control performance for reference tracking and disturbance rejection by learning from past model-system errors. The efficacy of the LPNMPC is evaluated through several simulations using a validated SCF model from the CIESOL research center located at the University of Almería, Spain. Comparative analyses against existing PNMPC strategies demonstrate the LPNMPC’s capability to eliminate offset errors, address significant model discrepancies, and maintain low computational effort. Results indicate a slightly better performance of the LPNMPC compared to the conventional PNMPC, achieving up to 13% fewer errors in scenarios with significant model uncertainty, emphasizing the LPNMPC’s control efficiency. The new LPNMPC has been experimentally tested in the CIESOL facility, exhibiting smooth control performance, accurate reference tracking, and satisfactory temperature regulation during cloudy days. The results obtained in the real facility validate the applicability of the LPNMPC in real-world settings, achieving fast reference tracking and no overshoot response.

Index Terms—Nonlinear model predictive control, Learning-based predictive control, Solar thermal power plant, Solar energy

I. INTRODUCTION

SOLAR energy is a renewable solution that can replace fossil fuels and other unsustainable energy sources. To achieve this goal, efforts to enhance the efficiency of solar energy use are essential. In the domain of solar thermal energy,

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Igor M. L. Pataro, Juan D. Gil, José D. Álvarez, José L. Guzmán, and Manuel Berenguel are with Centro Mixto CIESOL, ceiA3, Universidad de Almería. Ctra. Sacramento s/n, Almería 04120, Spain (emails: ilp428@inlumine.ual.es; juandiego.gil@ual.es; jhervas@ual.es; joguzman@ual.es; beren@ual.es).

João M. Lemos is with INESC-ID, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisbon, Portugal (email: jmlm@inesc-id.pt).

endeavors are geared towards improving the efficiency of Solar Collector Fields (SCFs). This system harnesses solar irradiance, absorbing it in the collectors and transferring radiation to thermal energy within the pipes. The Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) flows through the pipes, delivering thermal power to various demand-side systems, such as absorption chillers and heat exchangers for cooling and heating buildings [1], [2], desalination processes [3], [4], distillation industry [5], [6] and power generation [7].

Effectively controlling the HTF outlet temperature is crucial to determining the solar thermal plant’s overall efficiency [8], [9]. This objective is achieved by controlling the HTF flow rate since the amount of sun irradiance is never manipulated. From a control engineering perspective, managing SCF systems is challenging due to their highly nonlinear dynamics, disturbances, and uncertainties in model parameters. These complexities require advanced automatic control strategies for effective control [10], [11].

Numerous studies have explored advanced control strategies for SCF [12]–[26]. Based on the literature review, controllers using nonlinear models combined with Model Predictive Control (MPC) are among the most effective for controlling SCFs due to their ability to address various concerns within a single framework [9], [27], [28].

Regarding nonlinear strategies, the Practical Nonlinear Model Predictive Controller (PNMPC) [29] has proven to be an outstanding solution to deal with the SCF nonlinear dynamic, providing low computational effort by the continuous linearization of the nonlinear model [30]–[35]. Research suggests that PNMPC has significantly reduced computational effort, similar to linear MPC approaches, while maintaining equivalent closed-loop performance and disturbance rejection capabilities comparable to Nonlinear MPC (NMPC) [36]. Nevertheless, there is still room for investigation of PNMPC regarding large model errors, ramp reference tracking, and closed-loop behavior associated with prediction errors and disturbance rejection. This work contributes to addressing these issues concerning the performance of PNMPC in SCF systems.

The results presented in [34] have inspired further studies. The authors presented the PNMPC controller that considers the integral of the filtered error to correct the output model predictions when there are model uncertainties issues. However, as presented by the authors, the the proposed solution is problematic when large model errors arise, which can lead to instability in closed-loop, given the inclusion of an integrative action in the error feedback. On the other hand, in [36], the

authors have proposed an error feedback framework similar to the Dead-Time Compensator Generalized Predictive Controller (DTC-GPC) filtered Smith predictor to eliminate the offset error in the PNMPC approach. Conversely, the PNMPC robustness and stability regarding severe model uncertainties must be considered by increasing the filter time constant, which can compromise the closed-loop performance and the correction of offset errors.

Based on the previously mentioned concerns, the main objective of this work is to propose a Learning PNMPC (LPNMPC) strategy to address larger model errors (related to parameters and delay uncertainties) that still affect the performance of practical nonlinear predictive controllers for SCF. Inspired by the Multistep, Multivariable Adaptive Regulator (MUSMAR) algorithm [15] and learning-based MPC (LBMPC) strategies [37], the new LPNMPC solution provides an adaptive parametric function called the Oracle, using past pseudostates of the plant through Recursive Least Squares (RLS) with Exponential Resetting (ER) [38]. The goal is for the Oracle function to learn from the system's current data to capture the unmodeled dynamic caused by unmeasured disturbances and internal model mismatches so it can predict future errors and improve output prediction accuracy. In this proposed algorithm, the Oracle parameters estimate the PNMPC model errors while the ER algorithm prevents the Oracle RLS covariance matrix from winding up, improving the convergence of the least-squares computing.

The features presented in the LPNMPC are motivated by actual scenarios faced while controlling the SCF system:

- 1) Larger model errors arise due to varying time delay and model parameter uncertainties, such as heat losses and irradiance gain. These issues can bring instability in closed-loop, which still is an unaddressed aspect in PNMPC solutions [34],
- 2) Learning from data and predicting the model error has effectively improved performance in LBMPC controllers [37], [39]. This solution can enhance reference tracking for the PNMPC strategy, thereby promoting better efficiency in solar thermal plants.
- 3) SCF systems present particular scenarios due to saturation of the input variable. Therefore, implementing RLS in these situations may cause a wind-up of the covariance matrix and lead to instability due to malfunctioning of parameter estimation [38]. This condition is avoided by using the ER+RLS, and the parametric Oracle function can be identified properly when the HTF flow saturates.

Therefore, this paper introduces a new approach to controlling SCF systems, primarily focusing on enhancing the performance of practical nonlinear predictive controllers in addressing large-model errors. Furthermore, the study contributes to the field of control engineering by introducing new features, such as the Oracle function, which enables model adaptation based on learning data. Lastly, the paper shows the applicability and effectiveness of the LPNMPC through its implementation in an existing facility, providing empirical evidence of its utility and efficacy.

In this work, the new LPNMPC approach is compared with the solutions shown in [34] and [36], which are the main current contributions in the bibliography to treat the control issues using the PNMPC in SCFs. To do so, an existing SCF located in the CIESOL (Solar Energy Research Center, in Spanish) research center at the University of Almería is used as a case study. The CIESOL SCF model validation procedure is described to guarantee the adequate system modeling necessary to develop the LPNMPC. Furthermore, the LPNMPC algorithm is implemented in the existing CIESOL SCF system under different scenarios and meteorological conditions to strengthen the effectiveness of the results.

This work is organized as follows: Section II presents the LPNMPC formulation, including the model linearization algorithm, the Oracle function construction, and the control optimization problem. In Section III, the LPNMPC is proven compared to the stable PNMPC [34] and the PNMPC with filtered error [36] under several possible scenarios using a validated CIESOL SCF model. Section IV discusses the results of the actual implementation of the LPNMPC in the CIESOL facility. Finally, in Section V, the main considerations and conclusions are given.

II. LPNMPC CONTROL ALGORITHM

This section outlines the main aspects of the LPNMPC strategy. First, the model linearization algorithm is presented, followed by the Oracle function for estimating model errors. Finally, the control law is derived from the formulated control optimization problem.

A. PNMPC prediction equation

The comprehensive development of the PNMPC strategy can be found in [29]. To reduce the computational cost of the nonlinear optimization problem of conventional NMPC strategies, the PNMPC uses a repetitive linearization of the system's nonlinear model.

First, the natural evolution of the nonlinear system called the free-response vector \mathbf{F}^1 is computed as

$$\mathbf{F} = f(\overleftarrow{\mathbf{Y}}, \overleftarrow{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{u}_0, \overleftarrow{\mathbf{d}}, \mathbf{d}_0), \quad (1)$$

in which f defines as the nonlinear system dynamic as a function of the vector of the past outputs $\overleftarrow{\mathbf{Y}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \cdot n_l \times 1}$, the vector of past manipulated inputs $\overleftarrow{\mathbf{u}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u \cdot n_l \times 1}$, the vector of past disturbances $\overleftarrow{\mathbf{d}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_d \cdot n_l \times 1}$, and the current measured input and disturbances $\mathbf{u}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ and $\mathbf{d}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_d}$, respectively. The vector dimensions are associated with the number of n_y outputs, n_u inputs, n_d disturbances, and the order of the past values n_l . To represent the past vectors mathematically, consider a particular example for the output $\overleftarrow{\mathbf{Y}}$, that can be expressed as

$$\overleftarrow{\mathbf{Y}} = [y_1(k-1), y_1(k-2), \dots, y_1(k-n_l), y_2(k-1), \dots, y_2(k-n_l), \dots, y_{n_y}(k-1), \dots, y_{n_y}(k-n_l)]^\top. \quad (2)$$

¹Herein, the bold type notation denotes matrices and vectors, while scalar variables are represented as cursive notation.

The vector $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \cdot N_p \times 1}$ is the prediction of the nonlinear model, in which N_p is the prediction horizon. From the instant k to $k + N_p$, the input and disturbance increments are 0, resulting in the system's natural evolution. At each instance $k + j$, for $\forall j = [1, N_p]$, the discrete values of the estimated future outputs $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ are obtained considering a sample time T_s .

The forced response is computed as a linear approximation of the nonlinear model based on the Taylor-series expansion truncated in the first term, here called $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \cdot N_p \times n_u \cdot N_c}$ and $\mathbf{G}_d \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \cdot N_p \times n_d \cdot N_p}$, respectively, considering N_c as the control horizon (usually $N_c \leq N_p$).

Let $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ be the predicted outputs computed by the nonlinear model. Thus, considering the first-order Taylor expansion defined as

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = f(\overleftarrow{\hat{\mathbf{Y}}}, \overleftarrow{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{u}_0, \overleftarrow{\mathbf{d}}, \mathbf{d}_0) + \left. \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}} \right|_{\mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{d}_0} \Delta \mathbf{u} + \left. \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{d}} \right|_{\mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{d}_0} \Delta \mathbf{d}. \quad (3)$$

Defining the forced response matrices as

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+1)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}(k)} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+2)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}(k)} & \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+2)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}(k+1)} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \cdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+N_p)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}(k)} & \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+N_p)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}(k+1)} & \cdots & \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+N_p)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}(k+N_c-1)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{G}_d = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+1)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{d}(k)} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+2)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{d}(k)} & \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+2)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{d}(k+1)} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \cdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+N_p)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{d}(k)} & \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+N_p)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{d}(k+1)} & \cdots & \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(k+N_p)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{d}(k+N_p-1)} \end{bmatrix},$$

the approximated linear model prediction of the PNMPC is

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{F} + \mathbf{G} \Delta \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{G}_d \Delta \mathbf{d}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{G} = \left. \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}} \right|_{\mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{d}_0}$, $\mathbf{G}_d = \left. \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{d}} \right|_{\mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{d}_0}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{u} = [\Delta \mathbf{u}(k|k), \Delta \mathbf{u}(k+1|k), \dots, \Delta \mathbf{u}(k+N_p-1|k)]^\top$ and $\Delta \mathbf{d} = [\Delta \mathbf{d}(k|k), \Delta \mathbf{d}(k+1|k), \dots, \Delta \mathbf{d}(k+N_p-1|k)]^\top$. To account for future disturbance increments, it is necessary to estimate the disturbance dynamics from $k+1$ to $k+N_p-1$, which can be used in any model representation. Moreover, the notations $(k+j|k)$ denote the predicted or estimated variables at instant $k+j$ given the arbitrary instant k .

As observed, the nonlinear model dynamic $f(\overleftarrow{\hat{\mathbf{Y}}}, \overleftarrow{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{u}_0, \overleftarrow{\mathbf{d}}, \mathbf{d}_0)$ can be approximated by a linear representation of the future inputs and disturbances increments. This practical formulation is worthwhile for developing MPC strategies since the conventional Quadratic Programming (QP) optimization problem can be straightforwardly imposed. Moreover, matrices \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{G}_d are computed numerically, considerably reducing the algorithm's computational burden.

B. Parametric Oracle function for error estimation

In this work, the future model error is learned from the current plant data using a parametric Oracle function. As will

be demonstrated in the next sections, the proposed solution is advantageous over previous work since the Oracle function does not include any integrative term in the error prediction, being more robust under large model error scenarios. In addition, estimating future errors improves the output prediction, presenting better closed-loop performance. Moreover, the error estimation converges based on the ER+RLS algorithm [38], which can eliminate offset error.

For the sake of simplicity, consider a Single Input Single Output (SISO) scenario for better understanding. The parametric Oracle function is defined as

$$\mathcal{O}(k) \approx \hat{e}(k) = \boldsymbol{\psi}^\top \mathbf{s}(k). \quad (6)$$

Here, \approx denotes equality in the least squares sense, and the model regressors are expressed as

$$\mathbf{s}(k) = [y(k-1), \dots, y(k-n_{y_s}), u(k-1), \dots, u(k-n_{u_s}), d(k-1), \dots, d(k-n_{d_s}), e(k-1), \dots, e(k-n_{e_s})]^\top, \quad (7)$$

and the error $e(k) = y(k) - \hat{y}(k)$ is the difference between the actual system output and the model prediction. Although $\mathbf{s}(k)$ is not unique for all types of plants and may not represent all the system realizations, it is a sufficient statistic to estimate future plant outputs, hence being called *pseudostates* [15]. Moreover, n_{y_s} , n_{u_s} , n_{d_s} , and n_{e_s} are the regressor orders assumed for the outputs, inputs, disturbances, and errors, respectively. As noted, the regressors' orders are parameters selected to model prediction errors within the system. Hence, the choice of Oracle regressor orders should align with the potential dynamics encountered in studying the system model, providing valuable insights for tuning selection. Let the parameters $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ be written as

$$\boldsymbol{\psi} = [\psi_1, \psi_2, \dots, \psi_{n_s}]^\top, \quad (8)$$

where $n_s = n_{y_s} + n_{u_s} + n_{d_s} + n_{e_s}$. The main purpose of the Oracle function is to use the actual system's past pseudostates to predict and estimate future errors. Using the MUSMAR model identification algorithm makes it possible to estimate the set of parametric functions to compute $\hat{e}(k+j|k)$ for all $j = 1, \dots, N$, considering a generic prediction horizon N^2 .

Therefore, the future estimated error can be obtained in the form of

$$\Theta(\mathcal{O}(k)) = \Phi^\top \mathbf{s}(k), \quad (9)$$

where

$$\Theta(\mathcal{O}(k)) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{O}(k+1|k) \\ \mathcal{O}(k+2|k) \\ \vdots \\ \mathcal{O}(k+N|k) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

Matrix Φ^\top comprises a different set of parameters for each predicted instant j , which contributes to avoiding model error propagation.

²Note that the Oracle prediction horizon N is not necessarily equal to the model prediction horizon N_p . Further details about the complete algorithm are given in Appendix A

Using the proposed Oracle function on the PNMPC linear prediction model in Eq. (5) and extrapolating for Multiple-Inputs and Multiple-Outputs (MIMO) situations, the LPNMPC output prediction is defined as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} = \underbrace{\mathbf{F} + \mathbf{G}\Delta\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{G}_d\Delta\mathbf{d}}_{\hat{\mathbf{Y}}} + \Theta(\mathcal{O}(k)), \quad (11)$$

in which

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} = [\tilde{y}(k+1|k), \tilde{y}(k+2|k), \dots, \tilde{y}(k+N_p|k)]^\top. \quad (12)$$

As can be seen, the proposed formulation of LPNMPC learns from the system data (pseudostates) and adjusts the internal prediction model to match the actual system outputs.

C. LPNMPC optimization problem

Based on the presented output prediction (Eq. (11)), the LPNMPC optimization problem is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\Delta\mathbf{u}} J_{LPNMPC}, \\ J_{LPNMPC} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N_p} |\tilde{y}(k+i|k) - y_{ref}(k+i|k)|_{\mathbf{Q}}^2 \\ + \sum_{l=0}^{l=N_c-1} |\Delta u(k+l|k)|_{\mathbf{R}}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

subject to:

$$\begin{aligned} u_{min} \leq u(k+l|k) \leq u_{max} \quad \forall l \in [0, N_c-1], \\ \Delta u_{min} \leq \Delta u(k+l|k) \leq \Delta u_{max} \quad \forall l \in [0, N_c-1], \\ y_{min} \leq \tilde{y}(k+i|k) \leq y_{max} \quad \forall i \in [1, N_p], \\ \tilde{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{F} + \mathbf{G}\Delta\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{G}_d\Delta\mathbf{d} + \Theta(\mathcal{O}(k)). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where the input limits are u_{min} , Δu_{min} , u_{max} , and Δu_{max} , the output limits are y_{min} , and y_{max} , and matrices \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} are the tuning weight parameters to the reference tracking error and the input increment effort. Parameters Δu_{min} and Δu_{max} are related to the actual process capabilities of varying the input, while u_{min} and u_{max} and y_{min} , and y_{max} are the actual process input and output bounds, respectively.

Remark 1: The LPNMPC robustness performance regarding model mismatches, although lacks a rigorous stability formulation, depends not only on the MPC tuning (N_p , N_c , \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{R}) but also on the Oracle function parameters (the error prediction horizon N and the pseudostates orders n_{y_s} , n_{u_s} , n_{d_s} , and n_{e_s}). The selection of these parameters must be carefully chosen based on the insights into the system behavior, sensor delays and noise, and the model accuracy, which can impact the error estimation and, thus, the control robustness.

The general LPNMPC strategy can be represented as shown in Figure 1. Assuming that the Oracle function is estimated online, the error model will converge to the actual error between the output prediction $\hat{y}(k)$ and the system output $y(k)$, when $k \rightarrow \infty$, which guarantees a steady-state error elimination. The proposed formulation follows the results presented in [36], in which the general control scheme is based on the Filtered Smith Predictor controller [40]. Herein, the filter can be interpreted as the Oracle function, estimating the

Fig. 1. LPNMPC control scheme

error between the model and the process using the system regressors $s(k)$.

Remark 2: Since the LPNMPC control strategy uses the ER+RLS estimation, it is required to impose a forced excitation in the system observation. Therefore, a small amplitude white dither noise $\eta(k)$ is added to the current optimal control action computed by the optimization problem Eq. (14), such as

$$u(k) = \mathbf{I}_u \Delta\mathbf{u} + u(k-1) + \eta(k). \quad (15)$$

for \mathbf{I}_u being the proper receding horizon vector to capture only the first optimal solution of $\Delta\mathbf{u}$.

Finally, it can be noted from Figure 1 that the disturbance model is required to predict future disturbance behavior. This aspect can be resumed to the conventional PNMPC formulation when considering $\Delta\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{0}_{nd \times 1}$, which assumes that a step-form disturbance approximates the forecast of the disturbance dynamic. The proposed LPNMPC controller is detailed in the Algorithm 1.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the LPNMPC is tested and compared in a simulation environment with two proposed PNMPC solutions, here denoted PNMPC-i (with the integral of the filtered error) [34], and conventional PNMPC with the filtered error correction [36]. The goal is to explore the algorithm's advantages and robustness for large error, reference tracking, and disturbance rejection scenarios.

A. CIESOL SCF model calibration

In this study, the SCF of the CIESOL facility is used as a case study. The description of the solar thermal plant can be found in [33]. A lumped-parameters model is used to capture the dynamic of the SCF HTF outlet temperature [41], described through the nonlinear differential equation

$$\frac{dT_{sc,o}(t)}{dt} = f(T_{sc,o}(t), T_{sc,in}(t), T_a(t), I(t), q(t)) \quad (16)$$

Algorithm 1 LPNMPC control law algorithm

1. **Initialize.** Obtain the nonlinear system model $f(\cdot)$ and the disturbances model for Δd and define the control parameters Q , R , u_{min} , Δu_{min} , u_{max} , Δu_{max} , y_{min} , and y_{max} , the regressors orders (n_{y_s} , n_{u_s} , n_{d_s} , n_{e_s}) and the Oracle prediction horizon N .
 2. **Measure the system.** Measure the past inputs \overleftarrow{u} , outputs \overleftarrow{Y} , and disturbances \overleftarrow{d} of the actual system and the related pseudostates $s(k)$.
 3. **Compute the free response.** Simulate the nonlinear model using the model's past states, keeping the future input and disturbances increments 0 for the defined prediction horizon N_p .
 4. **Compute the forced response.** Apply small increments in the future inputs and disturbances and calculate the gradient of the outputs in relation to the free response.
 5. **Estimate the Oracle parameters.** Using the pseudostates $s(k-N)$ and the past model errors $e(k-N)$, estimate the Oracle parameters Φ^T through the ER+RLS solution (see A).
 6. **Predict the model error.** Using the pseudostates $s(k)$ and the identified Φ^T , compute the Oracle prediction $\Theta(\mathcal{O}(k))$.
 7. **Linear output prediction.** Design the following LPNMPC output prediction model

$$\tilde{Y} = F + G\Delta u + G_d\Delta d + \Theta(\mathcal{O}(k)).$$
 8. **Obtain optimal control actions.** Solve the QP in Eq. (13) and obtain the future optimal input increments.
 9. **Implement the control action.** Apply just the first control action $\Delta u^*(k|k)$ in the actual system
 10. **Receding horizon.** Move to the next instant, and repeat Steps 2 to 10.
-

for the nonlinear function is

$$f(T_{sc,o}(t), T_{sc,in}(t), T_a(t), I(t), q(t)) = \frac{\beta}{\rho \cdot C_p \cdot A_{sc}} \cdot I(t) - \frac{H}{\rho \cdot C_p \cdot A_{sc} \cdot L} \cdot \left(\frac{T_{sc,o}(t) + T_{sc,in}(t - t_{d_{T_{in}}})}{2} - T_a(t) \right) - \frac{q(t - t_{d_q})}{A_{sc} \cdot c_f} \cdot \frac{T_{sc,o}(t) - T_{sc,in}(t - t_{d_{T_{in}}})}{L}, \quad (17)$$

where $T_{sc,o}(t)$ [°C] is the HTF outlet temperature, $T_{sc,in}(t)$ [°C] is the HTF inlet temperature, $I(t)$ [W/m²] is the solar irradiance corrected by the tilt angle of the collector field, and $T_a(t)$ [°C] is the ambient temperature. Concerning the control aspects, the manipulated variable is the HTF flow $q(t)$ [m³/h], and the controlled variable is $T_{sc,o}(t)$. The time delay $t_{d_{T_{in}}}$ is related to the inlet temperature, and t_{d_q} is associated with the water flow rate. The model parameters β , H , A_{sc} , C_p , ρ , L and c_f are, respectively, the irradiance efficiency and conversion factor related to the dimension of the collectors [m], global heat losses coefficient [W/°C] per equivalent L tube length, pipe cross-section area [m²], the specific heat capacity of the water [J/kg°C], water density [kg/m³], equivalent absorber tube length [m], and the conversion factor from hours to seconds and for the equivalent one individual collector loop length [s/h]. The complete study of the system dynamic model can be encountered in [9]. In this work, $t_{d_{T_{in}}}$ and t_{d_q} are approximated as the mean value obtained empirically (and the uncertainty associated with this choice will be addressed by the proposed control structure).

In Eq. (17), parameters β and H remain inherently uncertain due to various environmental factors, including collector dirt, air conditions, and ambient temperature. In this context, a classical offline least-squares optimization method is used to calibrate parameters β and H . The proposed optimization

Fig. 2. Validation test of the CIESOL SCF model on September 14, 2023.

problem is defined as

$$\min_{\hat{H}, \hat{\beta}} J_m, \quad (18)$$

$$J_m = \sum_{k=0}^{k=N_T} \left(\hat{T}_{sc,o}(k) - T_{sc,o}(k) \right)^2,$$

subject to model dynamics in discrete time (discretized using the forward Euler method) and the H and β maximum and minimum limits

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}_{sc,o}(k+1) &= f(\hat{T}_{sc,o}(k), T_{sc,in}(k), T_a(k), I(k), q(k), \hat{H}, \hat{\beta}), \\ \hat{T}_{sc,o}(0) &= T_{sc,o}(0), \\ H_{min} &\leq \hat{H} \leq H_{max}, \\ \beta_{min} &\leq \hat{\beta} \leq \beta_{max}, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $\hat{T}_{sc,o}(k)$ is the model temperature, $T(k)$, $I(k)$, $T_a(k)$, $u(k)$ are the actual data of the system and $\hat{T}_{sc,o}(0)$ is the model outlet temperature in the initial sample time $k=0$.

The model calibration procedure encompassed the first experiment on September 13, 2023, in which various step variations in the HTF water flow were done to cover distinct operational ranges within the SCF. On that day, the irradiance profile during this experiment showed transient behavior due to passing clouds. Subsequently, the *fmincon* solver, available in the Matlab Optimization toolbox [42], was used to determine the optimal value for $\hat{\beta}$ and \hat{H} , by minimizing the cost function in Eq. (18). Moreover, the model delays are also estimated, observing the variable's reaction (inlet and outlet temperature and water flow changes) at each step. The parameter constraints were set to $\beta_{min} = 0.2$ m, $\beta_{max} = 0.4$ m, $H_{min} = 5$ W/°C and $H_{max} = 200$ W/°C following actual limitations of the plant behavior. On September 14, 2023, a validation test was conducted, replicating the earlier step-change procedure but on a clear-day irradiance scenario. Finally, the obtained optimal values $\hat{\beta}$ and \hat{H} from the calibration test are validated using data acquired on September 14, 2023. The validation data and the model performance graphics can be observed in Figure 2. As noted, the calibrated model can adequately represent the system dynamics for different temperature ranges and HTF flow rates. The model fitness is expressed numerically using the R-squared and the mean error between the model and the actual data, giving: $R^2 = 0.9847$ and $M_E = 0.594$ °C. Notably, the indices provided and the results in Figure 2

TABLE I
MODEL PARAMETERS VALUE FOR THE CIESOL SCF.

Parameter	Unit
A_{sc}	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$
c_f	$10 \cdot 3600 \text{ s/h}$
C_p	$4186 \text{ J/(kg} \cdot \text{°C)}$
\hat{H}	102.52 W/°C
L	46.6 m
$\hat{\beta}$	0.3882 m
ρ	972 kg/m^3
$t_{d_{T_{in}}}$	41 s
t_{d_q}	38 s

strengthen the model assertiveness capability, serving as a faithful representation of the nonlinear system dynamics for the LPNMPC implementation. Finally, the model parameter values from Eq. (17) are detailed in Table I.

B. Comparison simulation scenarios

Based on the validated SCF nonlinear model, the LPNMPC approach is proven and compared to the PNMPC-i and the conventional PNMPC. The experiments consider the same meteorological conditions, tuning parameters, and optimization problem described in Eq. (13) for all controllers. Here, the PNMPC-i presents a second-order Taylor approximation to computed \mathbf{G} and uses a constant value of the integral of the filtered error to correct the prediction. On the other hand, the conventional PNMPC includes the filtered error between the model prediction and the process output to adjust the prediction errors and imposes a first-order Taylor approximation to compute \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{G}_d matrices.

As described in [34], the PNMPC-i presents one tuning parameter for error feedback. The transfer function of the integral of the filtered error is defined as $h(z) = \frac{(z^2 - (1+f_d)z + f_d)}{(z^2 - (1+f_d - k_i)z + f_d)}$, in which f_d is the filter time constant and k_i is the integral gain. The authors propose the tuning parameter a following the desired dynamic of the model error as a second-order critically damped transfer function with denominator $(z - a)^2$. Hence, the parameters f_d and k_i can be obtained by equating the denominator $h(z)$ to $(z - a)^2$, giving $f_d = a^2$ and $k_i = 1 + a^2 - 2a$. On the other hand, the PNMPC [36] considers a low-order filter as a tuning parameter, defined as $F_r(z^{-1})$. The PNMPC and LPNMPC controller parameters are defined in Table II while the specific parameters a and $F_r(z^{-1})$ will be defined in the comparison scenarios subsequently. The parameters defined in Table II are chosen following the desired closed-loop performance, defining the closed-loop time constant as $\tau \approx 30 \text{ s}$. Note that the prediction horizon can forecast up to 120 s ahead, reaching up to the settling time for the approximated first-order system (prediction: $N_p \cdot T_s = 120$ and settling time: $4 \cdot \tau = 120 \text{ s}$). The input and output limits follow the actual CIESOL facility operational restrictions. Finally, for the disturbance predictions, the irradiance model is defined as an average of the irradiance increments from the previous 15 samples, while the ambient and inlet temperatures are kept constant along the prediction horizon since these variables present small variations during the normal operation of the SCF system. For the LPNMPC, the Oracle function

TABLE II
TUNING PARAMETERS FOR LPNMPC, PNMPC-I, AND PNMPC.

Control Parameters	Values
T_s	5 s
N_p	24
N_c	6
\mathbf{Q}	$40 \cdot \mathbf{I}_{N_p}$
\mathbf{R}	$10 \cdot \mathbf{I}_{N_c}$
Δu_{max}	$5 \text{ m}^3/\text{h} \cdot T_s$
Δu_{min}	$-5 \text{ m}^3/\text{h} \cdot T_s$
u_{max}	$15 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$
u_{min}	$3 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$
y_{max}	90 °C
y_{min}	50 °C

TABLE III
SIMULATION SCENARIOS FOR CONTROLLERS' PERFORMANCE COMPARISON.

Scenario	System conditions
Scenario 1	Parameters uncertainty (H and β 20% error)
	Delay error (15 s)
	Clear day irradiance
Scenario 2	Parameters uncertainty (H and β 20% error)
	Reference ramp tracking
	Clear day irradiance
	Input saturation
Scenario 3	Parameters uncertainty (H and β 20% error)
	Cloudy day irradiance

considers the regressor orders as $n_{y_s} = 2$, $n_{u_s} = 2$, $n_{d_s} = 2$ (set for the three disturbances: inlet and ambient temperatures, and irradiance), and $n_{e_s} = 2$, a random white noise dither of mean zero and variance 0.03 ($\eta \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.03)$), and the error prediction horizon as $N = 10$. Note that the design parameter N is smaller than the prediction horizon N_p , which implies that the solution proposed in A must be imposed. In addition, the covariance resetting tuning matrix is defined as $\mathbf{R}_\infty = \frac{0.08}{1-\lambda} \mathbf{I}_{n_s}$ following [38]. These assumptions are based on the behavior of the model error and the performance of the Oracle function to estimate the future error evaluated in several simulated experiments. On the other hand, the PNMPC-i strategy considers three tunings: aggressive $a = 0.65$, compromise $a = 0.7$, and conservative $a = 0.85$. The goal is to evaluate the sensitivity of the proposed tuning, including the integral error, to feed back the model predictions. Finally, the PNMPC is applied with a first-order filter $F_r(z^{-1}) = 0.1393/(z - 0.8607)$ to correct the prediction errors where the parameters have been selected after systematic empirical tests.

The simulation experiments are resumed in Table III. The system conditions are proposed to emulate an actual control situation in the CIESOL thermal facility. In all scenarios, the LPNMPC, PNMPC-i, and PNMPC controllers are used to control the nonlinear validated model (Eq. (16)) with the parameters defined in Table I

The first experiment (**Scenario 1**) is shown Figure 3. The objective is to observe the controllers' performance when a considerably high model error and delay mismatch arises from the SCF's varying delay behavior. For the sake of simplicity, only the PNMPC-i best compromise tuning ($a = 0.7$) is shown. As observed, the presented LPNMPC can properly control the SCF HTF outlet temperature, eliminate the offset

Fig. 3. Scenario 1 comparison results.

error, and present a very smooth behavior. As detailed in the zoomed region in Figure 3, the LPNMPC method presents a slight improvement compared to the PNMPC strategy, delivering a smoother response in cases of significant model errors. Notably, the PNMPC-i and the conventional PNMPC lose performance when time-delay differences arise in the model mismatch, presenting a more oscillatory behavior. On the other hand, similar to the closed-loop performance of Scenario 1, the LPNMPC maintains very smooth control throughout the experiment, as can be noted in the highlighted regions in the transitory moment of reference changing in Figure 3.

The second test (**Scenario 2**) investigates the ramp reference tracking and input saturation aspects. The saturation scenario is generated intentionally to evaluate the ER+RLS approach for the LPNMPC Oracle function. The main issue is that when using an RLS approach in this situation, the input is poorly excited, and the data observations behave nonlinearly regarding the input and output, causing a wind-up of the covariance matrix. Therefore, the proposed resetting of the covariance matrix is investigated when the Oracle function tries to estimate the future error.

Scenario 2 results are detailed in Figure 4. An unattainable reference is imposed between 15 h and 16 h to generate a saturation scenario. Nevertheless, although the system is poorly excited, the LPNMPC maintains smooth control after returning the reference to a feasible point. It can be noted from the zoomed graphics in Figure 4 that the LPNMPC responds faster to the ramp reference tracking, approximating more to the setpoint signal when compared to the PNMPC and the PNMPC-i. Moreover, the ER+RLS estimation performance can be noted in Figure 5, in which the eigenvalues λ_e of matrix P are presented. Note that the eigenvalues keep a smooth trend even though the poor excitation of the system affects the RLS computation. Finally, Figure 6 shows the results for (**Scenario 3**) in a cloudy-day situation. Once again, the LPNMPC and the PNMPC show very similar behavior, contrasting with the PNMPC-i, which presents a poor performance in regulating the HTF temperature when strong disturbances affect solar irradiance. Notably, the LPNMPC can circumvent the input saturation issues when computing the Oracle prediction with the ER+RLS approach. Table IV summarizes each strategy's index for the proposed scenarios. The Sum of the Absolute Error (SAE) between

Fig. 4. Scenario 2 comparison results.

Fig. 6. Scenario 3 comparison results.

the temperature reference and the HTF outlet temperature is used as an error metric. The control effort is estimated by the Sum of the Control Increments (SCI) index, measuring the HTF variations during the experiments. Moreover, the mean elapsed time (t_{proc}) during the controller computation of a single action is used as a manner to estimate the computational effort. The simulations were performed in an Intel Core i7-7700 CPU 3.6 GHz, 16GB RAM computer using MATLAB[®] R2019b from Mathworks, with the *quadprog* solver and the YALMIP toolbox [43]. To study the LPNMPC performance regarding the learning Oracle function, Figure 7 details the Oracle estimation. As can be seen, the Oracle function estimates precisely the future error one sample time ahead, even when strong disturbances in the solar irradiance affect the system, demonstrating a crucial feature to address

TABLE IV
CONTROLLERS PERFORMANCE INDICES FOR SCENARIOS 1, 2, AND 3.

		LPNMPC	PNMPC-i (a=0.65)	PNMPC-i (a=0.7)	PNMPC-i (a=0.85)	PNMPC
Scenario 1	SAE [°C]	369.03	533.98	461.98	379.22	396.89
	SCI [m ³ /h]	110.91	98.19	90.54	73.28	103.03
	t _{proc} [s]	148.10	150.19	148.91	150.33	151.22
Scenario 2	SAE [°C]	969.29	1041.10	1115.90	1229.03	1007.60
	SCI [m ³ /h]	154.27	123.35	113.87	90.31	90.55
	t _{proc} [s]	136.50	138.58	134.11	138.02	140.25
Scenario 3	SAE [°C]	1471.40	4807.10	1774.70	1447.20	1446.40
	SCI [m ³ /h]	472.43	542.67	242.46	188.92	208.87
	t _{proc} [s]	156.87	157.27	157.94	157.65	157.40

Fig. 7. LPNMPC Oracle function estimation for one sample ahead prediction for Scenarios 1, 2, and 3.

an offset-free performance for the LPNMPC.

C. Feasibility aspects

A final simulation is proposed to demonstrate the practical feasibility of the LPNMPC, wherein the LPNMPC controls the SCF with different prediction horizon tunings. In this simulation, Scenario 1 conditions are repeated (see Table III). To analyze the model's delay error for different prediction horizons, for predictions shorter than $N_p = 11$ (the approximated minimum for the model delay $t_{d_q} = 53$ s), the model delay is considered one sample time shorter than the prediction horizon, $t_{d_q} = N_p - 1$. In addition, to facilitate the comparison, it is considered $N_c = N_p$ to reduce the complexity of analyzing different tunings for each parameter.

The results can be evaluated in Table V, which provides the SAE, SIC, and the Sum of the Normalized cost function (SJ_n) for several control tunings. Moreover, Figure 8 shows the corresponding graphics of the performance index as a function of the prediction horizon.

From the proposed tunings used for the LPNMPC applied to the SCF, the minimum prediction horizon tuning wherein the LPNMPC remains stable is $N_p = 6$. From this initial point of Figure 8, it is evident that as the LPNMPC horizon grows, the controller's performance reduces, increasing all indices. However, an optimal condition can be met between $N_p = 7$ and $N_p = 10$, in which the minimal SAE and SJ_n indices are obtained. This phenomenon primarily stems from the match of the process and model delays when N_p is around 8, reducing the delay mismatch. Moreover, the "U"

TABLE V
PERFORMANCE INDICES FOR DIFFERENT LPNMPC PREDICTION HORIZONS.

N_p	SAE	SCI	SJ_n
6	522.69	95.20	88.92
7	400.40	82.26	47.85
8	342.79	59.25	39.8
9	341.03	57.33	37.48
10	347.45	58.25	40.04
11	381.40	59.98	44.40
12	373.00	89.01	33.36
13	373.03	84.83	35.38
15	374.66	81.10	42.63
16	376.61	84.79	49.03
24	379.81	84.69	77.12

Fig. 8. Performance metrics for different LPNMPC prediction horizons.

shape form of the curve is commonly found in predictive control strategies analysis in which the valley originates due to the approximation of the steady-state Linear Quadratic (LQ) control behavior. However, when elongating prediction horizons, the model predictors lose precision, and hence, the performance degrades, as observed in Table V.

The result of the different tuning of the LPNMPC aligns with conventional predictive strategies and provides satisfactory insights into the acceptable performance of controlling SCF. Despite significant model errors and differing control tuning, the LPNMPC consistently achieves stable and expected outcomes, demonstrating feasibility aspects for implementation in real experiments.

D. LPNMPC performance discussion

First, it was shown that the LPNMPC could adequately eliminate offset errors in considerably high model uncertainty

scenarios, improve disturbance rejection, and enhance ramp reference tracking compared to conventional PNMPC strategies. As depicted in Table II, the LPNMPC obtained the best performance for the output error in Scenarios 1 and 2, with an improvement of 13 % and 4 % on the SAE index compared to the PNMPC. These capabilities arise from the proposed Oracle learning function, which can use the system data information to predict the model errors and thus achieve reliable output predictions. Furthermore, including the Oracle function estimation in the control algorithm does not reflect more computational effort since, as shown in Table IV.

Second, the results presented in Figures 5 and 7 suggest that the LPNMPC features are feasible even though input saturation and strong high-frequency disturbances affect the SCF. Moreover, as noted in Section III-C, the LPNMPC has adequate behavior under significant model errors for different control tuning, which brings reliable results for real implementation.

The PNMPC-i [34] showed high sensitivity regarding the tuning parameter a , where more aggressive tuning resulted in system oscillations, risking instability. Treating the prediction error with an integral term is very concerning since this approach could potentially compromise the closed-loop performance in real systems due to parameter uncertainty. This issue warrants careful investigation before any practical implementations are considered. Similarly, the design parameter $F_r(z^{-1})$ of the PNMPC [36] is crucial to determine the closed-loop performance in the case of model uncertainties, in which a faster filter dynamic could generate a prompt correction with the drawback of presenting a more oscillatory behavior. On the contrary, a slower filter time constant could provide a slower response in closed-loop, compromising the error correction.

Finally, defining the Oracle function horizon N and the regressor's order is crucial to estimating the prediction error properly. Similar to the PNMPC filter $F_r(z^{-1})$ and the PNMPC-i tuning a , LPNMPC tuning can be designed to increase robustness or provide a more aggressive response. Thus, deep insights from the system's dynamic and model parameter uncertainties must be evaluated previously in simulation experiments since no systematic rule can yet be proposed.

IV. LPNMPC IMPLEMENTATION IN THE CIESOL SCF

After evaluating the LPNMPC performance in a simulation environment, the new strategy is tested in the actual CIESOL facility. The controller is implemented as designed in Section III-B, only including a low-order filter for the irradiance signal to avoid abrupt changes in the HTF flow rate due to high-frequency disturbances. The calibrated model without any modification is considered as the internal nonlinear controller model using the validated parameters of Table I. Also, the proposed irradiance prediction model and the assumptions for the ambient and inlet temperatures defined in Section III-B are replicated in the real experiment.

The LPNMPC is implemented over the CIESOL facility's already regulatory control framework, where a PI with an anti-wind-up controller regulates the pump frequency to achieve the desired HTF flow. Moreover, due to the plant operational conditions during the experiments, the maximum flow rate

Fig. 9. LPNMPC applied in the CIESOL SCF on November 14, 2023.

Fig. 10. LPNMPC applied in the CIESOL SCF on November 15, 2023.

was reduced to 12 m³/h as the two accumulation tanks were operating, causing a considerable load loss in the system.

The first experiment was conducted on November 14, 2023, as shown in Figure 9. On that day, the solar irradiance was disturbed by passing clouds. Nevertheless, the LPNMPC could handle the disturbance and present satisfactory reference tracking for different operating points. In this experiment, it was shown that the proposed white-noise dither was not sufficient to stimulate the system due to resolution limitations of the temperature sensors and the pump inverter. Consequently, the alterations in the flow rate did not generate significant effects on the HTF output temperature data. Regardless, this drawback did not impact the experiment, as implementing the ER+RLS algorithm can circumvent this issue [38]. On November 15, 2023, a clear-day experiment was conducted in which the LPNMPC was evaluated for different step reference changes. The results in Figure 10 show that the learning-based predictive controller could satisfactorily deal with the nonlinear dynamic of the SCF system. In addition, the presented closed-loop response obtained a time constant of approximately 27 s on average, which is very close to the desired response designed in Section III-B. In this test, an operational maneuver changed the valve positions in the CIESOL facility, which caused an unmeasured disturbance around 11.3 h. However, the LPNMPC could quickly return to the reference after correcting the conditions. The final test was performed on November 17, 2023, in which an induced saturation of the HTF flow occurred. The intention is to evaluate the performance of the ER+RLS when this issue affects the real-world experiment. It can be noted from Figure 11 that unattainable references

Fig. 11. LPNMPC applied in the CIESOL SCF on November 17, 2023.

Fig. 12. LPNMPC Oracle function obtained in the experiments in the CIESOL SCF on November 14, 15, and 17, 2023.

were imposed around 12.5 h, 14.5 h, and 15.5 h. Similar to the simulated Scenario 3, the covariance matrix of the ER+RLS method converged, keeping the error estimation and the computation of the Oracle function regardless of the data's poor excitation. These results are also seen in Figure 12, where the Oracle estimation converges to the actual error between the model and the actual SCF system. As seen in practice, the LPNMPC can effectively control the SCF system, presenting smooth control, precise reference tracking, and promising temperature regulation for cloud-day scenarios. Consequently, the results that were achieved strengthen the use of the LPNMPC on actual systems, aiming to guarantee the adequate operation of SCF systems in solar thermal plants.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduces a new learning-based nonlinear MPC (LPNMPC) for SCF systems, incorporating an Oracle learning function to predict future errors between the model and the actual system. The LPNMPC solves important issues related to large model errors in the conventional PNMPC presented in the literature. The LPNMPC framework effectively addresses issues such as offset-free control, robustness in severe model mismatch scenarios, and low computational effort using the PNMPC algorithm. It also improves the estimation of the Oracle function through ER+RLS, overcoming practical issues related to poor data excitation.

The LPNMPC showed superior performance compared to PNMPC with a robust filter, reducing errors by 7 %, 13 %, and 4 % in scenarios with high model errors, delay mismatch,

and ramp tracking, respectively. This improvement would be even greater in large solar plants with parabolic collectors due to the high temperatures involved. However, LPNMPC, like other MPC strategies, requires careful tuning of numerous parameters, directly affecting error estimation and closed-loop performance. While the Oracle function does not increase computational costs, it may complicate the controller's design.

Future work will compare LPNMPC with other learning-based approaches, further investigate its tuning parameters to analyze their impact on performance and study stability criteria for LPNMPC using Lyapunov function formulations.

APPENDIX

The parametric Oracle function is proposed to estimate the PNMPC model's future error, following a linear equation defined as

$$\mathcal{O}(k) \approx \hat{e}(k) = \psi^\top s(k). \quad (20)$$

Hence, the parameters set ψ is identified by applying the ER+RLS algorithm (see [38] for a complete description of the algorithm), solving the optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\psi} J_{\mathcal{O}}(\hat{\psi}), \\ = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^k \lambda^{k-i} \left[e(i) - \hat{\psi}^\top s(i) \right]^2, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

given k observation points and $\hat{\psi}(k+1) \triangleq \operatorname{argmin}_{\hat{\psi} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_s}} J_{\mathcal{O}}(\hat{\psi})$. The parameter λ , known as the “forgetting factor”, is a number chosen from 0 and 1. Commonly, this parameter is chosen between 0.95 and 0.995. The solution to the ER+RLS problem is computed recursively as

$$\hat{\psi}(k+1) = \hat{\psi}(k) + \mathbf{K}(k) \left[e(k) - \hat{\psi}(k)^\top s(k) \right], \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{K}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n_s}$ is denoted as the Kalman gain, given by

$$\mathbf{K}(k) = \mathbf{R}(k+1)^{-1} s(k), \quad (23)$$

Following the exponential resetting algorithm [38], the information matrix $\mathbf{R}(k) = \mathbf{P}(k)^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_s \times n_s}$, wherein $\mathbf{P}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_s \times n_s}$ is the covariance matrix, is updated as follows

$$\mathbf{R}(k+1) = \mathbf{R}(k) - (1-\lambda)(\mathbf{R}(k) - \mathbf{R}_\infty) + s(k)^\top s(k). \quad (24)$$

Matrix $\mathbf{R}_\infty \in \mathbb{R}^{n_s \times n_s}$ is a positive definite matrix used as a factor designed to tune the exponential resetting of the information matrix, and, as a consequence, the covariance matrix resetting, avoiding the wind-up effect [38]. This estimation gives parameters $\hat{\psi}(k+1)$ for the Oracle function. Nevertheless, the main objective is to predict $\hat{e}(k+j)$, for $j = 1, \dots, N$, estimating the future error based on the system pseudostates. Therefore, the future error estimation is proposed by using the following predictor model

$$\hat{e}(k+j) = \hat{\psi}_j s(k). \quad (25)$$

Since at instant k , $y(k+j)$, $u(k+j)$, and $d(k+j)$ are not available for $j \geq 1$, the parameter estimation is delayed N sample times in order to use the past $s(k-N)$ to estimate

ψ_j . This solution is inspired by the MUSMAR algorithm [15], which provides an adaptive predictive control law. Hence, the ER+RLS equations (Eq. (22) to Eq. (24)) are also delayed in time, using the regressors and the observations from $k - N$ to k . The predictive error models, for all $j = 1, \dots, N$, are obtained as

$$\hat{\psi}_j(k+1) = \hat{\psi}_j(k) + \mathbf{K}(k) [e(k-N+j) - \mathbf{s}(k-N)^\top \hat{\psi}_j(k-N)], \quad (26)$$

$$\mathbf{K}(k) = \mathbf{R}(k+1)^{-1} \mathbf{s}(k-N), \quad (27)$$

and

$$\mathbf{R}(k+1) = \mathbf{R}(k) - (1-\lambda)(\mathbf{R}(k) - \mathbf{R}_\infty) + \mathbf{s}(k-N)^\top \mathbf{s}(k-N), \quad (28)$$

Equation (26) is defined for each j , and, correspondingly, for each $\hat{\psi}_j$. For instance, if $j = 1$, the ER+RLS estimates $\hat{\psi}_1$ for the error in $e(k - N + 1)$ using the delayed regressors $\mathbf{s}(k - N)$ and the delayed estimated parameters $\hat{\psi}_1(k - N)$ (the conventional RLS delayed N samples). For $j = 2$, a different parameter set $\hat{\psi}_2$ is obtained for the observation of error $e(k - N + 2)$ using the estimated parameters $\hat{\psi}_2(k - N)$ and the same regressors $\mathbf{s}(k - N)$, which means that a different set of parameters are used to estimate two steps ahead using the same amount of information. The algorithm continues until $j = N$, which means that it predicts up to the current instant k .

After estimating the matrix Φ^\top , the Oracle model predicts the future model error using the recent regressors $\mathbf{s}(k)$, obtaining the following model predictor

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{O}(k+1|k) \\ \mathcal{O}(k+2|k) \\ \vdots \\ \mathcal{O}(k+N|k) \end{bmatrix}}_{\Theta(\mathcal{O}(k))} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \psi_{1,1} & \psi_{2,1} & \cdots & \psi_{N,1} \\ \psi_{1,2} & \psi_{2,2} & \cdots & \psi_{N,2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \psi_{1,n_s} & \psi_{2,n_s} & \cdots & \psi_{N,n_s} \end{bmatrix}}_{\Phi^\top} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} y(k-1) \\ \cdots \\ y(k-n_{y_s}) \\ u(k-1) \\ \cdots \\ u(k-n_{u_s}) \\ d(k-1) \\ \cdots \\ d(k-n_{d_s}) \\ e(k-1) \\ \cdots \\ e(k-n_{e_s}) \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{s}^{(k)}} \quad (29)$$

The overall Oracle prediction model is summarised in Figure 13.

Remark 3: As the regressor $\mathbf{s}(k - N)$ remains consistent across all predictive models $\hat{\psi}_j$, both the Kalman gain update (Eq. (27)) and the covariance matrix update (Eq. (28)) are common to the future predictive models. Therefore, these updates are executed once per iteration, significantly minimizing the computational burden.

As noted in [15], separating the set of parameters for each predicted instant, that is, $\hat{\psi}_j$ for $j = 1, \dots, N$, circumvents the estimated error propagation issue when nonlinear models are addressed, the model order is not properly captured, or exogenous inputs are not considered. In an ideal scenario

Fig. 13. Oracle function prediction scheme

where the plant behaves linearly and possesses a known order, the separate estimation of predictors becomes unnecessary, as the model error would be constant. However, this approach proves advantageous in practical scenarios of nonlinear systems by enhancing predictive performance. Estimating $\hat{\psi}_j$ for $j = 1, \dots, N$ outperforms extrapolating the one-step-ahead predictor, resulting in an adaptive control algorithm. This algorithm, at least within local contexts, dynamically adjusts the error model to minimize underlying costs and progresses in a Newton direction [15].

The ER+RLS algorithm establishes a covariance matrix resetting, which is advantageous for the proposed error estimation when poor system excitation compromises the RLS data variations. The excitation solution is commonly obtained by including a white dither noise with a small amplitude in the LPNMPC computed increments, as will be detailed in the next sections. In the case that exponential resetting is not applied and poor excitation occurs, the information matrix approaches $0_{n_s \times n_s}$, which results in the wind-up of the covariance matrix.

A. Tuning the Oracle prediction horizon

As proposed in Section II-B in Eq. (11), the Oracle function is an error estimation for the PNMPC model prediction. Hence, to address the same dimension of the output predictions $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}$, the Oracle prediction horizon can be tuned as $N = N_p$.

As noted, the Oracle function has two model calibration concerns: tuning the regressors' order ($n_{y_s}, n_{u_s}, n_{d_s}, n_{e_s}$) and the error prediction horizon (N). Although no formal development is proposed to tune these parameters, system insights are essential to define the regressor's order, considering the open-loop dynamic, for instance, first-order, second-order systems, or high-frequency output noise [15]. Moreover, the PNMPC prediction horizon N_p is crucial to tuning the Oracle prediction horizon. Note that the regressors' delay increases

as the prediction horizon increases. This characteristic can lead to undesired outcomes in Oracle predictions since the MPC tuning parameter N_p is strictly related to the closed-loop performance, the system dynamics, and stability [44]. In this case, long horizons involve the use of significantly older delayed regressors in computing $\Theta(\mathcal{O}(k))$, where the data obtained at $(k - N_p)$ (when $N = N_p$) might not accurately represent the recent plant information at k . Consequently, using the set of models Φ may result in poor predictions of future errors.

To tackle this issue, a proposal involves tuning the Oracle horizon N for longer prediction horizons N_p . The solution is to adhere to the previous formulation for $j = 1, \dots, N$, defining $N < N_p$, and then replicate the last estimated value of the Oracle function $\mathcal{O}(k + N)$ up to N_p to match the dimensions of the output predictions. Using this method, more recent and precise plant observations are used, focusing primarily on extrapolating only the furthest predicted error ($\mathcal{O}(k + N)$). Essentially, this adaptation ensures that recent predictions ($\mathcal{O}(k + 1)$ to $\mathcal{O}(k + N)$) remain reliable, offering a more accurate estimation of future errors. This enhanced approach is valuable within a receding horizon strategy such as the LPNMPC, in which only the first computed control action of the control horizon is implemented in the actual system. Therefore, the most important control action that actually affects the controlled system is computed with reliable information.

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Igor M. L. Pataro received a B.S. degree in Process Control and Automation Engineering and an M.S. degree in Mechatronics Engineering from the Federal University of Bahia, Salvador, Brazil, in 2016 and 2019, respectively, with an international master’s research period at the Università degli Studi di Padova, Italy, (2018). He is currently pursuing a Ph.D. degree in Computer Engineering with the University of Almería, Spain, with a doctorate abroad scholarship from Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq), Brasília,

Brazil. His main research interests include modeling, control, and optimization of processes and renewable energy systems, with an emphasis on predictive control, nonlinear control, and system optimization.

Juan D. Gil received a B.S. degree in Industrial Electronic Engineering, an M.S. degree in advanced and Industrial Computing and in Industrial Engineering, and a Ph.D. in Computer Science from the University of Almería in 2015, 2016, 2019, and 2020, respectively. He also obtained the laurea in Ingegneria dell’Automazione Industriale from the University of Brescia (Italy) in 2016. Currently, he is an Assistant Professor at the University of Almería. His research activity is mainly focused on the implementation of hierarchical and predictive

control strategies for solar-powered membrane desalination systems and solar thermal systems.

José D. Álvarez received the Computer Science Engineering degree and Ph.D. degree in automatic control in solar plants from the University of Almería, Almería, Spain, in 2003 and 2008, respectively. He is a member of the Automatic Control, Electronics, and Robotics Group with the University of Almería, Almería, Spain. His research interests are focused on the fields of repetitive control, MPC, PID control, and control education, with applications to solar power plants and user’s building comfort.

José L. Guzmán received the B.S. degree in computer science engineering from the University of Almería, Spain, and the European Ph.D. degree (extraordinary doctorate award) from the University of Almería, Spain, in 2002 and 2006, respectively. He is a Full Professor of automatic control and systems engineering at the University of Almería. His research interests focus on the fields of control education, model-predictive control techniques, PID control, and robust control, with applications to agricultural processes, solar plants, and biotechnology.

He has been a member of the Spanish Association in Automatic Control CEA-IFAC since 2003 and the IFAC Technical Committee on Control Education, and the IEEE Technical Committee on System Identification.

João M. Lemos is a professor of systems, decision, and control in the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal, and coordinator of the Control of Dynamic Systems research group at INESC-ID. His interests are concerned with applications of predictive, adaptive, and distributed control. Solar thermal systems, thermoelectric power plants, water delivery canals, and biomedical applications of control, including anesthesia and HIV-1 infection, are the main topics addressed.

Manuel Berenguel received the B.S. and M.S. degrees in industrial engineering and the Ph.D. degree (Hons.) from the University of Seville, Seville, in 1992 and 1996, respectively. He is currently a Professor of Automatic Control and Systems Engineering at the University of Almería, Spain. His current research interests include predictive and hierarchical control, with applications to solar energy systems, agriculture, and biotechnology. He is co-author of the books *Advanced Control of Solar Plants* (Springer, 1997) and *Control of Solar Energy*

Systems (Springer, 2012). He has been a member of the IEEE Control Systems Society since 2000 and a Senior Member since 2014.